

PREDICTIVE METHODOLOGY FOR PROGRESSIVE MATRIX CRACKING-DELAMINATION INTERACTION: INTERNAL CONSTRAINT EFFECTS OF GENERAL LAY-UP COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, a new methodology for progressive matrix cracking-local delamination interaction of general lay-up composites has been developed. The proposed methodology is unique in that it extends the constitutive description of homogeneous elastic media with distributed cracks to laminated composites and uses a five-layer equivalent constraint model (ECM) to investigate the internal constraint effects on damage evolution. By this rather unique approach, the intractable problems of internal constraint effects on interactive damage progression of matrix cracking and local delamination can be handled in a systematic manner.

INTRODUCTION

Polymeric composites develop matrix cracks parallel to the fiber directions under fairly low levels of applied loads. The density of the cracks increases with load or with the number of fatigue cycles until reaching a saturation level denoted as "characteristic damage state" (CDS). Subsequently, the laminates develop inter-laminar delaminations and fiber breaks which lead to ultimate failure. Current models of progressive failure in polymeric composites pertain to predicting the establishment of the CDS, but cannot predict the onset and evolution of delaminations. However, since delaminations are much more *crucial* to the integrity of composite laminates than the transverse matrix cracks considered in the CDS analysis, the prediction of their initiation and growth is much more *relevant* for reliable designs.

It is in fact well documented by experimental observations that laminates develop extensive delaminations beyond the CDS stage, and the transition, interaction and evolution of the in-plane matrix cracking and delaminations depend largely on internal constraint effects between layers. It is also observed that the growth of delaminations portends the onset of massive number of fiber breaks which cause the final failure of the laminate. These observations have motivated several researchers to conduct investigations of delamination fracture at either free

edges or near matrix cracks. However, most of these investigations on delamination growth have been evaluated in association with an otherwise fixed geometry of matrix cracks of cross-ply laminates. Consequently, no rational methodology based on scientific understanding seems to exist at the present time to predict the internal constraint effects on the observed interactive growth of delaminations and matrix cracking. The main goal of this investigation is to extend the life prediction methodology for designing with composites beyond currently available limits. This goal will be achieved by developing a methodology to correlate the evolution of matrix cracks and delaminations within the lay-ups of composite laminates.

EXPERIMENTAL REPORTS ON INTERNAL CONSTRAINT EFFECTS

Since the 1970's, several experimental reports have confirmed that lamina strength is not an intrinsic lamina property, but a function of its constraint conditions. These observations emphasize the very important internal constraint effects of laminated composites on damage initiation and evolution. Recent experimental results obtained by Timmer and Hahn (1993) [1] are schematically shown in Fig. 1. The tests were conducted on a quasi-isotropic $[0_{\pm 45^0/90^0}]_{33}$ laminate of AS4/3501-6 graphite/epoxy composites. Matrix cracking in the 90^0 layers occurred first, followed by matrix cracking in the -45^0 layers, but there were no matrix cracks at all in the 45^0 layers. To determine the reason for this phenomenon, the constraint conditions of 45^0 layers and -45^0 layers were checked. From Fig. 1, we can see that the 45^0 layer and -45^0 layer were directly constrained by the strongest 0^0 layers and the weakest 90^0 layers, respectively. The much stronger constraint effects on the 45^0 layers offer much larger resistance to damage initiation than that on the -45^0 layers, and thus prevented matrix crack initiation in the 45^0 layers.

Figure 1 Matrix Cracking in $[0/45/-45/90_2/-45/45/0_2/45/-45/90]_3$ Laminate [1]

Presently, the existing analyses on internal constraint effects are limited to very special conditions. Most models have been developed for cross-ply laminates. The central problem

of this analysis (i. e. the theoretical framework of damage evolution under the current constraint conditions in a general lay-up composites) has not been formulated owing to a lack of effective models.

METHODOLOGY

This effort will include the following three components:

(1) *Establishment of an in-plane constitutive equation for any damaged ply*

In this approach, each ply will be considered as a homogeneous anisotropic layer. Consequently, this assumption will allow the employment of the constitutive formulations of Hill [2], Horii and Nemat-Nasser [3] which express the compliance of cracked elastic solids. Note that their work correlates compliance with damage for homogeneous media of finite volumes and under the general surface loading. Consequently, the above formulations can be applied at the ply level to express the in-plane stiffness $\bar{Q}_{ij}^{(k)}$ of any damaged k^{th} ply. It has already been established [4] that, for transverse matrix cracks, the damage-induced reductions of $\bar{Q}_{ij}^{(k)}$ are expressible as follows by some analytically derivable "control factors" $\Lambda_{2'2'}^{(k)}$ and $\Lambda_{6'6'}^{(k)}$ [4].

These factors depend not only on crack distribution and configuration in the k^{th} ply but also depend on the internal constraining effects imposed by the remainder of the laminate on the ply under consideration and they are named the "in-situ damage effective function" (IDEF). The important thing is that these factors are directly related to the average stresses and average strain in the ply at hand by

$$\Lambda_{2'2'}^{(k)} = 1 - \frac{\bar{\sigma}_y^{(k)}}{Q_{2'2'}^0(k) \bar{\epsilon}_y^{(k)} + Q_{1'2'}^0(k) \bar{\epsilon}_x^{(k)}} \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

$$\Lambda_{6'6'}^{(k)} = 1 - \frac{\bar{\sigma}_{xy}^{(k)}}{Q_{6'6'}^0(k) \bar{\gamma}_{xy}^{(k)}} \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

(2) *Equivalent constraint model (ECM) formulation.*

It may be suitable to account for the internal constraint effects, imposed on each damaged ply, in a way which can distinguish between the effects of the neighboring layers which are in direct contact with the generic k^{th} ply and the effects of the remaining layers. Since the geometric details of the remaining layers may be less important than that of the nearest neighboring layers, the remaining layers will be handled in an approximate manner. Specifically, all remaining plies above and below the nearest layers will be lumped into two equivalent homogeneous anisotropic layers, an upper group I_k and a lower group II_k . While all the geometric details in the adjacent $(k-1)^{\text{th}}$ and $(k+1)^{\text{th}}$ layers, such as the ply orientation, thickness and damage state will be considered in full detail, the corresponding properties of the remaining layers will be averaged out. In general, this consideration results in a five-layer equivalent constraint model (ECM) for a generic damaged layer k (Fig.2).

Figure 2 Five Layer Model for Matrix Cracking-Delamination Interaction

(3) A stress analysis for a representative unit cell within a fixed damaged configuration

A representative unit cell in the five-layer equivalent constraint model which represents a specific distribution and configuration of damage state within the k^{th} ply will be analyzed under prescribed equivalent constraint conditions. As noted in eqn. (1) the determination of the control factors IDEF requires the evaluation of stress and strain averages. To accomplish this, the representative unit cell is divided into sub-regions, such as those shown in Fig. 2 for a symmetric laminate, and then analyze each sub-region by means of the plate theory. This stress analysis resembles the method used by Armanios et al. [5]. Due to the symmetric conditions, only one quarter of the representative unit cell needs to be considered. Jointly with the boundary conditions and continuity conditions between subregions, this analysis cast an eigenvalue problem. The obtained eigenvalues λ_i and eigenvectors p_j^i ($i, j = 1, 2, 3$) are functions of geometric and material parameters of the five layers. The average stress and average strain can be expressed by a volume average of the stress and strain in the k^{th} ply. Substituting the obtained average stress and strain into eqn.(1), the control factors IDEF can be explicitly expressed. Take $\Lambda_{2,2}$ as example, it reads

$$\Lambda_{2,2} = \frac{(1 + \phi_1)(D^{dl} + \phi_2 D^{mc} F_1(\frac{1 - D^{dl}}{D^{mc}}))}{1 + \phi_1(D^{dl} + \phi_2 D^{mc} F_1(\frac{1 - D^{dl}}{D^{mc}}))} \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

where $D^{dl} = s/L$, $D^{mc} = h^{(3)}/s$. Φ_1, Φ_2, F_1 are functions of extensional stiffness $A_{ij}^{(k)}$, coupling stiffness $B_{ij}^{(k)}$, eigenvalues λ_i and eigenvectors $p^{(i)}$. Their explicit expressions will be listed elsewhere.

DAMAGE EVOLUTION

While the proposed methodology can readily handle the thermal effects on the energy release rate[4], these effects will not be discussed here for simplicity. In general, if ϕ denotes the total potential energy of a material body containing M cracks of areas A_m ($m=1, 2, \dots, M$), then the available energy release rate, $G^{(m)}$, associated with the growth of the m^{th} crack is given by

$$G^{(m)} = - \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial A_m} \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

When the generic k^{th} ply sustains damage by transverse cracking $D^{mc(k)}$ and by delamination $D^{dl(k)}$ ($k=1, 2, \dots, N$), the corresponding expressions for the energy release rates read [4]

$$G_{(k)}^{mc} = - \sum_r h^{(r)} \frac{\partial Q_{ij}^{(r)}}{\partial D_{(k)}^{mc}} \bar{\epsilon}_i^{(r)} \bar{\epsilon}_j^{(r)} \quad r = 1 \dots N, \quad \dots \dots \dots (5a)$$

$$G_{(k)}^{dl} = -1/2 \sum_r h^{(r)} \frac{\partial Q_{ij}^{(r)}}{\partial D_{(k)}^{dl}} \bar{\epsilon}_i^{(r)} \bar{\epsilon}_j^{(r)} \quad r = 1, \dots, N \quad \dots \dots \dots (5b)$$

where repeated indices, i and j, imply summation over their ranges (i, j=1, 2, 6). $D_{(k)}^{mc}$ is matrix crack density defined as $h^{(k)}/s^{(k)}$ and $D_{(k)}^{dl}$ is dimensional delamination length defined as $l^{(k)}/s^{(k)}$. They are related to the surface area of matrix cracks and delaminations through the matrix crack spacings $2s^{(k)}$ and delamination length $l^{(k)}$ (see Fig.2). In addition, $\bar{\epsilon}_i^{(r)}$ are the average strains in the r^{th} ply.

From eqns. (9a), (9b) and the relationship between the IDEF and $\bar{Q}_{ij}^{(r)}$, the energy release rate G^{dl} for delamination and G^{mc} for matrix cracking can be obtained from the derivatives of the IDEF with respect to D^{dl} and D^{mc} , respectively. Based on the calculations, the level of available fracture energies under the current constraint conditions by neighboring layers are evaluated and arranged in a hierarchical order for delamination VS. matrix cracking modes, with individual accounting for each damaged ply.

Griffith energy principle is used as a criterion for the evolution of damage in the form of matrix cracking and delamination. The damage scenario is generated by gradually incrementing the load amplitudes tracking the comparative ratios between levels of available and required fracture energies for competing matrix-cracking and delamination, and switching to new damage configurations for which the criterion of damage evolution has been satisfied.

RESULTS

Fig.3-5 are obtained from the approach proposed in this work. Fig.3 shows the critical matrix cracking density at which the transition from matrix cracking to local delamination occurs. It can be seen that as the thickness of the 90° layer increases the critical damage density C_d decreases. For the laminate $[0_4^0/\pm 45_4^0/90_1^0]_s$, the critical matrix crack density reduced from 20 to 5 cracks per cm when the number of the 90° layer increases from 1 to 5.

Fig.4 shows the internal constraint effects of three laminates with the same thickness of 90° layers on the critical applied stress $\sigma^{(l)mc}$ of initiation of matrix cracking and the critical stress $\sigma^{(l)dl}$ of transition from matrix cracking to delamination, respectively. From the lay-ups of the three laminates, we can see that the internal constraint effects on the 90° layer monotonically increases from the left laminate $[0_3^0/90_3^0/-45_3^0/90_{1.5}^0]_s$ to the right laminate $[0_3^0/90_3^0/0_3^0/90_{1.5}^0]_s$. The results that the critical stress are also monotonically increased from the left to the right show that the higher the constraint effects, the higher the required applied forces for initiation of matrix cracking and transition from matrix cracking to delamination.

Fig.5 shows the energy release rates G^{mc} for matrix cracking versus crack density C_d for the above mentioned three laminates. The results predict that as the internal constraint effects increases the available fracture energy G^{mc} decreases. This results explain the phenomena expressed in Fig.4, i.e., why the required tensile loading is much higher for the laminate $[0_3^0/90_3^0/0_3^0/90_{1.5}^0]_s$ than that for $[0_3^0/90_3^0/-45_3^0/90_{1.5}^0]_s$.

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

CONCLUSION

(1) A predictive methodology for interactive damage progression has been developed for general lay-up composites by accounting for internal constraint effects, through introduction of the in-situ damage effective factors (IDEF). The closed forms of the factors IDEF are determined via a micro/macrosopic analysis for a five-layer equivalent constraint model.

(2) The approach is rigorous and simple in predicting: (a) sequential anisotropic property degradations, (b) available fracture energy G for competing damage modes, and (c) initiation, transition and progression of damage modes.

(3) By this proposed unique approach, the intractable problem of laminate inhomogeneity effects on interactive damage progression can be handled in a systematic manner.

(4) This research has great potential to provide a rational methodology which enables the selection of lay-ups with improved damage resistance and increased service time for laminated composites, thereby enabling their improved design beyond currently available limits.

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